

Potential of Sago Plants in Lingga Regency Riau Islands Province

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ABSTRACT

Sago Metroxylonspis a palm family plant that stores starch in their stem. Sago plants are common in eastern Indonesia. Sago starchare used as a staple food or food industry. This is good at supporting food diversification so that Indonesia is not dependent on rice. Food needs such as rice in the Riau Islands, especially Lingga Regency were imported from outside the province. Though the potential/production of sago plants as a substitute for rice in LinggaRegency is quite high. In the western part of Indonesia, besides the largest sago-producing Riau Province, the Riau Islands province is also one of the sago producers in the Western Indonesia Region with an area of: 5,841 Ha, with a production of 3,324 tons, where the Lingga Regency is the largest sago-producing district in the Riau Islands land area: 3,449 (Ha) with production: 2,618 (Ton), scattered in 3 sub-districts namely Lingga District, East Lingga District and North Lingga District. The latest quarterly data states that 3,321 (Ha) of land planted by 1,126 farmers with 646.5 tons of sago production produced 1,594.9 kg of wet flour. With a wide and quite high production, Lingga Regency can be used as a center for the development of sago plants in Riau Islands.The problem that occurs is the use of sago waste that is not used optimally, therefore there is a need for technical guidance to the community about sago processing and post-harvesting of sago waste. This paper is expected to be an input for the local government, stakeholders and sago cultivators so that the results obtained can be maximized both in processing sago and waste to a minimum so that it can support agricultural development and food security in the district.

Keywords: Sago, Riau Islands, Lingga, food, potency

INTRODUCTION

Sago (*Metroxylon sp*) is one of the food crop commodities that can be used as a source of carbohydrates which is quite potential in the future. Sago is a plant native to Southeast Asia with its spread covering West Melanesia to East India, from North Mindanao to Java and southern Nusa Tenggara (Tahardi and Sianipar, 2001). Sago (*Metroxylon sp*) is one of the commodities with high carbohydrate content so it can be used as a source of carbohydrates besides rice,

corn, or cassava. Sago is used as food and industrial raw materials. Sago plants grow naturally, especially in plains or swamps with abundant water sources. Sago plants have the ability to grow on marginal land, so that sago plants become one of the mainstay sources of starch in the future. Sago production potential in Indonesia is estimated at 2 million tons per year. Plant area in Indonesia is estimated to consist of 1,250,000 hectares of forest and 148,000 hectares of plantation area. Sago production in Indonesia is spread in several regions including Irian Jaya, Sulawesi, Kalimantan, Riau Islands, Mentawai Islands (Flach, 1997).

Indonesia has a sago potential of around 50% of world sago production, and around 90% of Indonesia's sago potential exists in Papua, including West Papua (Jong and Widjono, 2007). The high potential of Indonesian sago can spur the development of Indonesia's sago industry. In Lampung, sago plants grow naturally in low areas. Quantitatively the sago population in Lampung is not enough to meet the raw material requirements for the sago industry. Some potential areas for sago plantations in Lampung are Palas 2, South Lampung Regency and LempasingTelukBetung Barat area (Kamalet al, 2000).

The processing of agricultural products produces products and waste in the form of waste. Waste is a waste that is not utilized and harms producers if it is not managed properly. Sago starch is obtained from sago stem extraction aged 5-8 years. Sago stems contain starch of 18.8% to 38.8% (wet weight), while in dry weight per plant can reach 250 Kg (Flach, 1997). The extraction process results in wasted water containing starch (Bujang and Ahmad, 2000). The sago industry generally carries out processing in areas near water sources such as on the banks of rivers or creeks, because sago stems from plantations or forests are brought to the place of production using water transportation. Sago processing industry with a large capacity can cause the accumulation of residual sago starch produced by sago processing. According to Bujang and Ahmad (2000), to produce 1 kg of sago flour, about 20 liters of wastewater will be produced. If this happens continuously, there will be an accumulation of sago waste which will cause river water pollution (Amos, 2010).

The existence of waste generated from the production process will become a constraint to business development if it is not handled properly which has the potential to damage the environment. Sago industry wastewater contains large amounts of organic material. The content of organic material contained in the sago industrial wastewater is in the form of starch, fiber, fat, and protein. According to Phang et al, 2000) in 3 Singhalet al, 2008) Sago industry wastewater has a very high ratio of carbon, nitrogen and phosphorus, namely (105: 0.12: 1). Organic material that is high enough in wastewater will affect the oxygen needs of microorganisms in degrading the organic matter.

The following are the potential benefits of sago plants (figure 1)

Figure 1. The potential benefits of sago plants

Local governments make the agricultural sector as a mainstay sector, in order to meet the increasing regional needs. The availability of agricultural products that are mostly from outside the province is very dependent on weather and ocean waves, so there is often a scarcity of an agricultural product. Based on this problem, it is an appropriate breakthrough to create food independence in a province (Izhar et al, 2014).

Based on the review and the problems mentioned above, it is necessary to conduct research on the potential development of sago plants in Lingga Regency. The results of the study as input in the preparation of future agricultural development plans. The purpose of the study illustrates the potential development of Sago plants in Lingga Regency, Riau Islands Province.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The study was conducted by survey method and visit to the location of agricultural production centers, especially sago plants. The study began with

coordination and consultation with a number of related institutions, among others: the Lingga Regency Agriculture and Forestry Service, Village Government, Field Extension Workers, and Farmers. The approach taken in the implementation of this study is the approach that adheres to the principles: participatory, dynamic and synergistic, linkages of researchers, extension agents and farmers. The participatory approach is expected to enable farmers to actively assess and assess the advantages and disadvantages of the technology that will be applied.

The activity begins with desk study and coordinates with relevant agencies and visits directly to the field to find out in detail the problems faced in the development of sago crop agriculture. Data collection in the form of secondary data and primary data. Activities are carried out in January - June 2018. Data collection uses interviews and discussions to produce secondary data and primary data.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Lingga Regency is one of the regencies located in Riau Islands Province. The area of Lingga Regency is 45.456,7 162 Km² which consists of land area of 2.117,72 Km² (4.66%), and the sea of 43.338,15 Km² (95.34%). The area consists of 531 large and small islands, not less than 95 fruits have been inhabited, while the remaining 436 pieces although not yet inhabited some have been used for various agricultural activities, especially in plantation business. Lingga Regency has a tropical climate with an average air temperature between 23.3 and 33.1 degrees Celsius. When viewed from the topography, most of the areas in Lingga Regency are hilly, there are 73,947 ha in the form of hilly areas, while the flat area is only about 11,015 ha. The most common types of soil are yellow red podzolic, litosol, and organosols and because the weather often changes so as to be used as agricultural land only certain plants can grow (Statistic Lingga Regency, 2015).

Lingga Regency is the main producer of Sago plants in Riau Islands Province. According to the Statistics of Riau Islands Province Statistics (BPS) that Lingga Regency is the highest Sago producer in Riau Islands Province. More specifically, we can see the data of the area (Ha), production (Ton) in the Riau Islands in Table 1.

Table 1. Planted Area of Sago Palm Plantation by Regency/Municipality in Riau Islands, 2013 - 2017 (Ha)

No	District/City	2013	2014	2015	2016 (ha)	2016 (Ton)	2017 (Ha)	2017 (Ton)
1	Natuna	-	-	-	252	10	252	10
2	Lingga	-	-	-	3.449	2.610	3.349	2.610
3	Karimun	-	-	-	2.075	692,2	2.075	692
4	Bintan	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
5	Kepulauan Anambas	-	-	-	65	4	65	4
6	Batam	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
7	Tanjung Pinang	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Total		-	-	-	5.841	3.324,2	5.841	3.324

Source: Agriculture, Forestry and Livestock Office of Kepulauan Riau Province

Note : In 2013-2015, data on the land area and production of Sago plants was not available at the Statistics of Riau Islands Province Statistics (BPS).

Lingga Regency consists of 2 big islands namely Daik Island and Singkep Island consisting of 9 sub-districts (figure 2), where 41.73%, the Lingga people work in the fields of Agriculture, livestock, fisheries, forestry and hunting.

Figure 2. Map of Lingga Regency of Riau Islands Province
 (Source: <http://petalengkap.blogspot.co.id>)

The people of Lingga Regency in addition to developing agricultural cultivation of horticultural crops, fruit crops. Plantation crops also make a large contribution to the income of Lingga Regency and have a fairly high area and

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production. Sago plant is the number 2 plantation which has the area and production in Lingga Regency.

Table 2. The Area and Production by Kind of Crops in Lingga Regency

Year Comodity	2013		2014		2015		2016		2017	
	Ha	Ton	Ha	Ton	Ha	Ton	Ha	Ton	Ha	Ton
Clove	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Sugar	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Palm	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Gambier	-	-	14,30	1,6	17	12	17	113	17	114,4
Cocoa	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Rubber	10.294,5	4.12	4.868,19	4.119,67	9.749,5	4.119	10.199,5	4.127	10.320,5	4.412
Coconut	2.696,75	1.267	1.356,40	1.247	2.696	1.275	2.694	1.290,6	2.694	1.301
Oil Palm	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Candlenut	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Coffe	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Pepper	122,89	36,02	87,8	37,95	142	37	148,5	43,8	167,5	48,60
areca nut	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Sago Palm	3.455	545	1.414,5	3.218	3.459	2.615	3.349	2.618	3.359	2.618
Total	16.569,14	5.968,02	7.741,19	8.651,22	16.043,5	8.158	16.391	6.113,04	16.588	8.494

Source: Department of Agriculture and Food Security of Lingga Regency

Sub-districts of Lingga, North Lingga and East Lingga are the three sub-districts with the highest order that have the most land area and production of Sago in Lingga Regency, with the final form of production, namely wet flour. Can be seen in Tables 3, 4 and figure 3.

Sago flour from Lingga Regency is sent to outside the district (Tanjungpinang and Anambas), because in TanjungPinang there are many culinary delights of Tarempa Noodle (Anambas Regency's typical food))

Table 3. The Area and Production of Sago Palm Plantation by Subdistrict in Lingga Regency

Year Sub -Distric	2013		2014		2015		2016		2017	
	Ha	Ton	Ha	Ton	Ha	Ton	Ha	Ton	Ha	Ton
Singkep Barat	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Singkep	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Singkep Selatan	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Singkep Pesisir	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Lingga	1.762	220	1.762	220	580	843	580	844	541	844
Selayar	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Lingga Timur	-	-	-	-	1.176	447	1.176	448	1.141	488
Lingga Utara	1.693	325	1.693	325	1.693	1.325	1.693	1.326	1.677	1.326
Senayang	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Total	3.455	545	3.455	545	3.349	2.615	3.349	2.618	3.359	2.618

Source: Department of Agriculture and Food Security of Lingga Regency

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Table 4. The planted area, production and total of farmer sago palmby Subdistrict in Lingga Regency

No	Sub-District	TBM (Ha)	TM (Ha)	TTM/R (Ha)	Total (Ha)	Production (Ton)	Farmers (KK)
1	SingkepBarat	-	-	-	-	-	-
2	Singkep	-	-	-	-	-	-
3	SingkepSelatan	-	-	-	-	-	-
4	Singkep Pesisir	-	-	-	-	-	-
5	Lingga	177	340	8	525	600	171
6	Selayar	-	-	-	-	-	-
7	Lingga Timur	774	188	198	1.13	595,74	364
8	Lingga Utara	659	828	179	1.1666	399,15	591
9	Senayang	-	-	-	-	-	-
Total		1.58	1.356	385	3.321	1.594,90	1.126

Source: Department of Agriculture and Food Security of Lingga Regency

Note: TBM : Haven't Producted Plantation Yet
 TM : Productive Plantation
 TTR : Breakage and Old Plantation

In Figure 4 (Colored Map) are 3 subdistricts in Lingga Regency which have sago plant centers and farmers scattered in Lingga District, North Lingga District and East Lingga District. The sago plantation in Lingga Regency is a legacy of the predecessor generation and has been cultivated for a long time.

Figure 3. Sago Flour from Lingga Regency

Figure 4. Center Planted area and Farmers in Lingga Regency (colored map)
 (Source: Department of Agriculture and Food Security of Lingga Regency)

Each region generally has superior commodities that have special taste compared to similar commodities in other regions so that if the commodity is developed optimally it will have a high level of production and selling value for the welfare of farmers. The strategy of agricultural development going forward in order to support agricultural revitalization is emphasized on the quality of superior commodities. Revitalization of agricultural development through the application of production technology, postharvest technology, efficiency in production costs up to marketing. Empowerment of farmers in rural areas also needs to be done with a focus on optimizing regional superior commodities aimed at the realization of a strong national agricultural sector and able to compete in the free trade market (Dirjenbun, 2014).

The selection of agricultural commodities must be site specific, quality, high production and open market opportunities are alternative farmers in carrying out their farming The decision aims to increase income and in turn to improve their welfare (Balitbangtan, 2012).

In Lingga Regency there is also a processing industry/post-harvest of plantation crops to accommodate plantation crops which are listed in table 5.

Table 5. Development of Agro Chemical and Forest Production in Lingga Regency, 2016

No	Classification	business unit	Investation	Employee (Person)	Production Value (000 Rp)
1	Cobra Industries	34	6.500.000	114	72.251.000
2	Sago Industries	244	2.933.012.000	457	3.380.000
	Total	278	2.9395.120.000	571	76.631.000

Source: Department of Labor Force, Small and Medium Enterprises, Industry of Lingga Regency

According to data from the Agriculture and Forestry Office of Lingga Regency that land that can be used as an area of agriculture, plantation and livestock grazing and forestry is not less than 80,000-190,097 Ha, while those that have been used (traditionally) are less than 25% (21,610 Ha). The plantation area that has been managed is 15,477 Ha while the potential of plantation land in Lingga Regency is 46,112 Ha, so the potential for development of the Sago area is still wide open.

Lingga Regency, although very potential for the development of sago plants, but efforts to increase the production of sago are often faced with various obstacles such as the availability of superior seeds, cultivation technology (Fertilization, Weeding, Pruning and Pest Management), integrated processing because the community considers that sago plants are plants sideline for land

that is considered to be less productive and without treatment, the results can still be taken. On average, farmers plant sago for the purpose of increasing income and consumption, because all parts of the sago tree such as the leaves and bark of the leaf midrib and bark can be used. Sago leaves can be made of roofs, baskets, mats or walls of the house, can be made broom. Sago bark is usually used as fuel. Not only that, sago flour is the final target of sago cultivation.

The extraction of sago flour contained in the pith is done by cutting the sago stems. In addition to being used as sago flour, it is also used as feed ingredients. Harvesting is done by farmers by cutting down sago stems, the time to determine harvesting for farmers there is no definite timing, farmers only see the size of the stem if the plant is large then it will be harvested. The types of sago scattered in Lingga Regency, Riau Islands Province, there are two types, namely Tuni/ Runggamanu *Metroxylon Rumphii Martius* Molat/Roe *Metroxylon Sagus Rottbol.*

In general, the types of sago that have the potential to be developed are Tuni sago type and Molat sago type because both types have high starch content.

Any obstacles faced by Lingga Regency farmers in Sago cultivation are the availability of superior seeds, pest control, handling of institutions that are still inadequate in production and marketing facilities. Some of the other constraints faced by Sago farmers in Lingga Regency are: low soil fertility and lack of labor, so that to manage the land, farmers have to spend quite high costs. Meeting the needs of very high organic materials is needed in increasing soil fertility.

Based on some of the existing problems, the technological innovations that will be offered are: introduction of superior sago types, application of production technology, postharvest technology, making organic compost, organic PPC manufacture from cow urine, making pesticide, integration of Sago and livestock, provision of alsintan . In addition, it is necessary to consider the determinants of Sago Bioindustry Agricultural Development. a) Availability of raw materials b) Availability of technology and assistance c) Availability of competent human resources (Entrepreneurship) d) Availability of markets and other institutions e) Availability of supporting policies (programs, capital, facilities and infrastructure).

The problem that occurs is knowledge about drinking water/sago pulp, where pulp cannot be managed properly / optimally, environmental pollution can cause environmental pollution. In sago processing there is waste or follow-up results in the form of bark and pulp. The pulp produced from this extraction process about 14% of the total wet weight of the sago stem (Flach, 1997). In production centers, waste Sago pulp is generally not utilized and just stacked up

which will eventually polluting the environment (Kompiang, 1995). Sago pulp (*Metroxylon sago*) is waste produced from sago processing, wherein the process is obtained flour and sago pulp in a ratio of 1: 6, which is rich in carbohydrates and other organic ingredients.

The pulp produced from this extraction process about 14% of the total wet weight of the sago stem (Flach, 1997; Rimalatu, 1981). Amount of waste that many, until now not yet utilized properly only left to accumulate on places processing of sago flour so that it causes environmental pollution. Sago has a lot of benefits and can have economic value, it only needs a touch of technology and innovation. Even if there are livestock who use it, only livestock located around the sago flour processing location, which directly consumes on the spot dregs without control. The potential of local raw materials in the form of waste agriculture, plantations and agro industry are very big, but only a small percentage used as feed. There are still many types of agricultural, plantation & agro-industrial waste untapped. Complete feed technology (complete feed) is one method/ technique of making feed used to improve waste utilization agriculture or plantation and agro-industrial waste through processing with physical treatment and supplementation for animal feed production poultry. The need for assistance how to make a product new to management after production.

Sago waste can be used as source material organic is also called ameliorant and vegetable herbicide. Besides containing phenolic acid and its effect as mulch, sago waste can work as a vegetable herbicide, the use of sago wastewater 100% in fresh form and decomposition to 1 effective month behind the weed company (Syakir, 2000). Lingga Regency is the center of pepper plants in Riau Islands, therefore the results of the waste can be utilized to support the growth of pepper plants that are location specific without having to bring in from outside. Sago pulp/repu has a very low protein value. The results of the analysis of the Suska Riau UIN Laboratory of Nutrition and Chemistry (2014) reported that the nutrient content of BK sago pulp was 47.20%, PK 0.83%, SK 11.44%, LK 0.99%, ash 1.80% and BETN 84.94%, and the content of ADF sago pulp fiber fraction was 13.79%, Lignin 10.34%, NDF 39.65%, Cellulose 1.74% and Hemicellulose 39.65%. Therefore, the need to touch technology to increase protein and energy content also reduces the content of NDF and ADF of sago waste (Simanihuruk, 2011).

Nutritional data shows that sago plantation waste and sago flour processing waste has the potential to be used as cattle feed ingredients. Nuraini et al. (2005). Reported that sago pulp in the form of laying fibers was obtained from solvents and squeeze the contents of the sago stem in processing the sago stem into sago flour. Pulp sago can be an alternative source of feed for energy

because it contains ingredients. Extract without nitrogen (BETN) is high at 76.51%. But it is not good if it is used as a single feed because it has a low crude protein content based on dry ingredients. To use it as animal feed, it needs to be fermented to improve nutritional value so that it can be given as a single feed or as a mixture of ingredients in complete feed. Waste from sago plantations is in the form of midribs and leaves, while the sago pulp is a sago stem processing waste into sago flour. Sago pulp is waste obtained in the processing of sago flour, which is in the process. The sago flour and pulp were obtained in a ratio of 1: 6 (Rumalatu 1981). The sago processing process produces follow-up waste in the form of bark about 17-25% and sago pulp 75-83% (McClatchey et al. 2006). Sago pulp can be utilized as a mixture of biogas substrate because it contains a lot of organic material especially elements of carbon and animal feed if processed properly (Lay & Patrik, 2010). It can be stated that sago waste has the potential as a source of cattle feed nice.

CONCLUSIONS

The prospect of developing sago plant cultivation in Lingga Regency is very good in the future. In addition to supporting regional food security as a source of carbohydrates, supporting the availability of animal feed, market opportunities and land potential are still wide open. However, it requires the support of technological innovations ranging from semi traditional to modern technology to meet guaranteed production and quality. Suggestions for local governments need to develop a road map for the development and processing of sago plants.

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